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Ecocriticism and Pandemic: from fictional to factual

Revista Letras Raras (RLR), a scholarly journal of Linguistics and Literature, from the Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity (Federal University of Campina Grande), launches the fourth regular edition of 2021. This issue focuses on Ecocriticism studies, by looking at the Coronavirus Pandemic, which still ravages the world, thus becoming the central emphasis of discussions and reflections presented here.

This issue is organised by professors Suênio Stevenson Tomaz da Silva, from the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), Sueli Meira Liebig, from the State University of Paraíba (UEPB), and Scott Slovic, from the University of Idaho (United States of America). Thereby, the four texts that make up the issue **Ecocriticism and Pandemic: from fictional to factual**, reveal how important the theme is and how much it is still taking its first steps in our country. In addition to the texts tied to the issue, this edition also has seven other papers that are not directly linked to the proposed thematic, but which are anchored in the large scope of the RLR.

This edition presents the collaboration of professors, students, and other scholars who are authors of papers, essays, translations, reviews, and texts of artistic or literary creation from different origins, such as: Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG), State University of Paraíba (UEPB), Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), FEEVALE University (Federation of Higher Education Establishments in Novo Hamburgo), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Federal University of Sergipe (UFS), Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA), Federal University of Southern Bahia (UFSB), Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), Federal University of Goiás (UFG), University of Brasília (UnB), and Federal University of Roraima (UFR).

Estimated readers, in this fourth regular edition, you will also be able to share these texts by pointing your mobile phone camera to the QR Code of the journal and to the text you wish to read. Dear readers, please share the paper, essay, poem, short story, interview, and the other texts in this issue, with your colleagues and students. Let us share language and literature, resisting the adversities that are imposed on us in face of so many difficulties, whether they are linked to denial or to so many other misadventures that we are currently experiencing. Let us resist and survive!

We finish this year among so many irreparable losses, in which we identify our dear Alfredo Bosi and so many other masters in Languages, paying our tributes to the families of the more than 619,000

Brazilians killed in this pandemic. Let us stay apart and share knowledge produced by science. Certain of this action, dear readers, we wish you a great reading!

Prof^a. Dr^a. Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz (UFMG, Brasil)

Prof^a. Dr^a. Maria Rennally Soares da Silva (UEPB, Brasil)

Editors of **Revista Letras Raras**: A Scholarly Journal of the Research Group LELLC – Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity / Federal University of Campina Grande.

Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral.